

Use of Web 2.0 Social Networking Sites for Collaborative Sharing Research Information by the Social Science Research Scholars at Alagappa University, Karaikudi.

P. Pitchaipandi, C. Baskaran

Abstract: This study attempts to the Web 2.0 Social Networking Sites for Collaborative Sharing Research Information by the Social Science Research Scholars at Alagappa University, Karaikudi. A sample size 97 Scholars was selected by random sampling method. The data required for the study were collected through a questionnaire. The findings of the study: 30.9% of the respondents using Facebook/ WhatsApp along with most highly used in the popular web browser used for Google chrome 72.2% Google chrome. 48.5% of respondents' preference of "Very Strongly Agree" Collaborate with Research projects and Teams. Whereas 46.4% "Research Collaboration "Strongly agree" of the respondents respectively. 30.9% purpose of Web 2.0 for Collaborations of Research Communication while 19.6% Opportunities and Learning for Web 2.0 tools support social interaction in the learning process of the respondents respectively.

Keywords: Web 2.0 tools, Collaborative learning, Sharing Research Information, Web 2.0 Opportunities, Blog/Wiki articles.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Social networking technologies have significant implication and these technologies can potentially be used in the information literate community to collect, organize and disseminate intellectual information to the user community. The term Web 2.0 refers to the Online Services that provides assurance collaboration, communication and information sharing. It represents and passive experience of static read only web pages to the participatory experience of dynamic and interactive web pages. Internet resources criteria guiding decisions can be considered a subject of criteria for electronic resources, Consideration should be given to the advantages and disadvantages of using pointers to remote resources at either the server level or the title level, providing reliable archival access, and downloading and maintaining internet accessible resources. When a digital library system is designed, it is assumed that there will be many indexes and a catalogue that can be searched to discover information before retrieving it form a repository. These indexes may be independently managed and support a wide range of protocols. Based on the work in services offered divided four parts: Collection service, naming service, repository services

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and indexing services. Respiratory service provides from simple deposit and access to digital objects to sophisticated management, aggregation and marshaling of the information stored in the repository².

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Baskaran, C. (2018) the study expertise that the use of social networks (SNs) and Medias through the research scholars in Alagappa University. M. Phil and PhD fulltime research scholars and their right to use of SNs/Medias devices tools. Face book, twitter, Whatsapp, Instagram, Google scholar, Research Gate etc. this study purpose of Search World Information, Sending Photographs, Forwarding new items, Meeting with friends, receiving and sending research articles. The researcher point of view observed SNs/Medias Barriers Confronted the research scholars¹. Baskaran (2014) investigation from the visit for Alagappa University Library access in information resources shows that Google, Yahoo, Alta vista, hotpot, Lycos, Northern light, Ask Jeeves, Sify is most popular search engine for accessing journals and e-books. The users visit the library for purpose of to prepare Projects/Seminars/assignments, to refer journal articles, to browse database². Baskaran, C.(2019) The studies explain of usage for social networks/medias in sharing scholarly information. This study focused on the four universities full time Ph.D social science scholars on Periyar University, Annamalai University, Madurai Kamarai University, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University. With a view to know the exposure of SNs and Media sources to the scholars at their social science or based on a structured questionnaire. The study confirmed that research scholars of social science are use of various types of SNs, Face Book, Twitter, and You Tube³. Baskaran, C., & Prasad, M. (2019) presented an analytic study of the status of electronic resources, faculties and services provided by the South Universities of Tamil Nadu. This study focused four Universities of Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Madurai Kamaraj University, Alagappa University, and Mother Teresa Women's Universities of South Tamil Nadu. The discussed the access to scholarly information through E-Resources, Place of Use to E Resources, Training provided for accessing E Resources, overall user satisfactions by the South Universities. Finally, the paper reported the results from questionnaire- based survey of e- resources use and its impact on South Universities users⁴.

Baskaran, C., & Binu, P. C. (2019) this study explained UGC-INFONET services and the use of e- resources by the Teaching faculty, Research Scholars and PG Students of Selected six state Universities of Kerala. i.e. Sree Sankarachary University of Sanskrit Kaladi, Cochin University of Science and Technology, University of Calicut, Mahatma Gandhi University, and University of Kerala, Kannur University with the exposure of UGC-INFONET and e-resources to the respondents at their faculty based on a structured questionnaire. The study confirmed that respondent of state Universities of Kerala are Purpose of the e-resources and use various types of CDs/DVDs, E-Books, E-Journals, E-Databases, E-Theses and Dissertations, E-Question Bank, Email alert services, OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue), and Institutional repositories, Digital Library services. The study suggested for the improvement in the access facilities and subscription of more e-resources for the respondents⁵. Tautkevičienė, G., & Dubosas, M. (2014) this study attempted survey should that the Purpose of their Web 2.0 tools for learning and Knowledge Updating for the students learning environment. Students' using web 2.0 tools priorities are using e-mail, Using personal management environment, Skype, Reading Wikis and blogs, Publishing video records, Subscribing RSS in etc., web 2.0 technologies into a formal education process. However, sometimes the possibilities, introduced by web 2.0, are not⁶. Williams, J. B., & Jacobs, J. (2004) this paper explain the prospective of blogs as learning spaces for students' in the higher education sector. This study favors of the blogs an effective to teaching and learning methods. The blog as a medium for facilitating learning and intermediate for student interactivity, reflection. Explores methods for using blogs for enlightening purposes in university courses. The experience of the Brisbane Graduate School of Business at Queensland University of Technology⁷. Chang, A. (2011) Presented an analytic study of Web 2.0 Social Networks sites and Face book marketing resources services provided by the participants. The web 2.0 applications support and creations support. Face book used can be online business use community building. There are three main businesses ways use of face book effectively namely of Community building marketing and promotion and Advertising management⁸.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify gender wise Contributions of the respondents
2. To identify the usage of Web 2.0 ,age group and Departmentt.
3. To study the use of Web 2.0 Websites.
4. To identify the different Purpose of using Web 2.0
5. To identify the Research Collaboration of Research Information.
6. To analyze Web 2.0 Opportunities and Learning.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this study survey method is used. A Further structure questionnaire was used for data collection required data from that study population. Questionnaires were distributed by the Social Science Research Scholars at Alagappa University, Karaikudi. The data collected was analyzed; the tabulated and interpreted data were analyzed by the sample percentage method in MS Excel to draw necessary inference. in the following.

Sampling Design: The researcher has decided to collect data from all the thirteen departments in Social Science of Economics and Rural Development / History , Education/ Physical Education, Social Work/Women Studies, Commerce/ Logistics Management, Library and Information Science, International Business / Corporate Secretary ship, Lifelong learning/Fine Arts. It was decided to get data from 150 respondents from each of the above thirteen departments. The researcher collected data from 150 M.Phil and Ph.D Research Scholars, she met in their concerned department on the day of her data collection work.

Method of data collection: The questionnaires were distributed to the M. Phil and Ph. D (full time) Research Scholars by the researcher personally. The duly filled in questionnaires were collected back from them immediately after they were filled. Out of 150 questionnaires distributed to the respondents, the research was able to get back only 97 duly filled in questionnaires.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The Researcher concerned with the distribution of questionnaire to use for data collection method. This study total number contribution of respondents (64.7%). A study out of 150 questionnaires distributes and 97 questionnaires received back only. (N=47) 48.5% male and (N=50) 51.5% Female respondents contributions of this study.

Table I: Sociodemographic Variables of study participants (N=97)

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	47	48.5
Female	50	51.5
Age Group		
20-25	46	47.4
26-30	27	27.8
31-35	16	16.5
Above 35	8	8.2
Avenue		
M. Phil	32	33.0
Ph. D	65	67.0

Table I the above table represents the Gender wise Contributions of them Respondents are Research Scholars of Alagappa University, Karaikudi. Observed that out of a total number of 97 research Scholars, in which a large majority contribution of 51.5% (N=50) Female and remaining 47 (48.5%) are from the category of Male. It can be interpreted that study population constitute with a greater proportion with female contributors than male ones. The age of the Social Science usually distributed in the range of 20 to above 35 years as shown in the above table. It is observed that a large majority of 46 (47.4%) of the Research Scholars belong to 20-25 years of age and then, Followed by 27 (27.8%) 26-30, 16 (16.5%) 31-35 whereas Above 35, 8 (8.2%) of age wise contribution of them respondents respectively.

The above table represents the Course wise distribution of Social Science Research Scholars of Alagappa University, Karaikudi.

Under study and observed that out of a total of 97 Research Scholars, in which a greater proportion of the study population 65 (67.0) are from Ph. D Research Scholar and remaining 33% (N=32) hails from M. Phil Scholars. It can be concluded that the majority of the research Scholars are from Ph. D Research Scholar.

Table- II: Department wise Respondents

Department	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Economics and Rural Development /History	11	11.3
Education/Physical Education	10	10.3
Social Work/Women Studies	6	6.2
Commerce/ Logistics Management	21	21.6
Library and Information Science	10	10.3
International Business / Corporate Secretary ship	27	27.8
Lifelong learning/Fine arts	12	12.4
Total	97	100

Table II represents the Department wise distribution of Social Science Research Scholars of Alagappa University, Karaikudi, that a majority of (N=27) 27.8% Research Scholar belong to International Business /Corporate Secretary ship discipline, Followed by 21.6% (21) of the research Scholars represents from Commerce/ Logistics Management background and then whereas 12 (12.4%) Research Scholars belongs to Lifelong learning/Fine arts. 11.3% (11) Research Scholars belongs to Economics and Rural Development /History furthermore 10.3% (10) of them Research Scholars belongs Education/Physical Education, Library and Information Science, while that 6.2% (6) of them Research Scholars of Social Work/Women Studies. The Department category wise distribution of Research Scholars in Alagappa University is also presented in graphical format.

Table III: Frequency of Using Web 2.0 tools

Web 2.0 tools	No. of respondents	Percentage
Face book/ WhatsApp	30	30.9
Twitter/ Instagram	18	18.6
Social bookmark / Tagging	16	16.5
RSS feeds/ Podcasts	8	8.2
Blog/Wiki articles	20	20.6
Other	5	5.2
Total	97	100

Table III observed from the above table that Research Scholars are mainly use the Web 2.0, 30 (30.9%) of the participants usage for Face book/ WhatsApp tools, Followed by 16 (16.5%) of them participants use of Blog/Wiki articles whereas 18 (18.6%) of the respondents belongs to usage for Twitter/ Instagram, 16 (16.5%) respondents are the beginners in using the web 2.0 Social bookmark / Tagging and 8 (8.2%) respondents are unable to use the RSS feeds/ Podcasts and 5

(5.2%) of respondents are unable to use of Other web 2.0 tools.

Table IV: Opinion on using Web Browser

Web Browser	No. of respondents	Percentage
Internet explorer	6	6.2
Mozilla fire fox	11	11.3
Google chrome	70	72.2
Opera	6	6.2
Others	4	4.1
Total	97	100

Table IV indicates the extent they use Web 2.0 Web Browser, results show that respondents Contribution of Google chrome were used very frequently by 70 (72.2%) respectively, Followed by Mozilla Firefox with 11 (11.3%) and Internet explorer, Opera with (6.2%). While that 4 (4.1%) of their respondents belongs to use other Web Browsers. It is expected that Web Browser like Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox and Opera will be the most visited Web Browser.

Table V: The Researcher Collaborative Sharing Research Information (CSRI) VSA- Very Strongly Agree, SA- Strongly, A- Agree, LA- Less Agree, NCs- No Comments

Research Work	VSA	SA	A	LA	NCs
Get in touch with other Researcher	19 (19.6)	42(43.3)	19 (19.6)	9 (9.3)	8 (8.2)
Disseminate the scholarly articles	31 (32.0)	30 (30.9)	7 (7.2)	9 (9.3)	20 (20.6)
Connect with Researcher Outside the academy	8 (8.2)	16 (16.5)	37 (38.1)	25 (25.8)	11 (11.3)
Research Collaborati on	20 (20.6)	45 (46.4)	12 (12.4)	9 (9.3)	11 (11.3)
Sharing Research Related Information with Friends.	34 (35.1)	25 (25.8)	23 (23.7)	8 (8.2)	7 (7.2)
To join educational communitie s	24 (24.7)	33 (34.0)	14 (14.4)	17(17.5)	9 (9.3)
Collaborate with Research projects and Teams	47 (48.5)	24 (24.7)	16 (16.5)	7 (7.2)	3 (3.1)

Table V shows the frequency of Web 2.0 Technologies for Collaborative Sharing Research Information by the Contributions of Social Science Research Scholars at Alagappa University.

42 (43.3%) of them respondents have rated Strongly. Agree feature of Web 2.0 Technologies Get in touch with other Researcher Followed by 30 (30.9%) respondents have rated the Disseminate the scholarly articles of Web 2.0 Technologies as Strongly Agree, 37 (38.1%) respondents rated Connect with Researcher Outside the academy features as Agree moreover 45 (46.4%) respondents rated Research Collaboration of Web 2.0 technologies Strongly Agree. While 34 (35.1%) respondents rated Sharing Research Related Information with Friends features as Very Strongly Agree, 33 (34%) respondents rated To join educational community features as Strongly Agree, While 47 (48.5%) respondents rated Collaborate with Research projects and Teams features of Web 2.0 Technologies as Very Strongly Agree of the respondents respectively.

Table VI: The Researcher Purpose of Web 2.0

Web 2.0 Purpose	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Research Communication	30	30.9
Group work	5	5.2
Targeted learning	9	9.3
Presentation learning materials	15	15.5
Dissemination of Information	18	18.6
Creation of Information	20	20.6
Total	97	100

Table VI shows the Purpose of Web 2.0 technologies Collaborative by the respondents. 30 (30.9%) Contributions of the participants opined that Research Communication purpose of using Web 2.0 tools. Followed by 20 (20.6%) respondents Creation of Information. While 18 (18.6%) respondents reason of Dissemination of Information, 15 (15.5%) of their respondents opined that it is the more preferred reasons for Presentation learning materials, 9 (9.3%) of the contributions purpose of Targeted learning and 5 (5.2%) of them participants purpose of Web 2.0 Group work information's are use of among the respondents under study.

Table VII: Opportunities and Learning with web 2.0 tools.

Discipline	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Web 2.0 tools helps Research Scholar engage with learning	14	14.4
Web 2.0 tools support social interaction in the learning process	19	19.6
Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to work at conceptual level of understanding	14	14.4
Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to develop critical thinking	18	18.6
Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to collaboratively build knowledge	17	17.5
Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to build their own knowledge	15	15.5
Total	97	100

Table VII describes the various Opportunities and Learning with web 2.0 Technologies for Collaborative Sharing Research Information, 19 (19.6%) Contributions of the respondents are belongs to learning Web 2.0 tools support social interaction in the learning process, Followed by 18 (18.6%) of the respondents contributions are Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to develop critical thinking moreover 17 (17.5%) Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to collaboratively build knowledge. Whereas 15 (15.5%) of the respondents contributions of Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to build their own knowledge furthermore 14 (14.4%) of the respondents contribution of Web 2.0 tools helps Research Scholar engage with learning and Web 2.0 tools enable Research Scholars to work at conceptual level of understanding of respondents are use the Web 2.0 Technologies.

VI. FINDINGS

1. To the highest (51.5%) of the participants using Web 2.0 technologies for CSRI belongs to Gender Category of Female, Followed by (47.4%) of them respondent age Group of 20-25 years.
2. To analyze that (67%) of them participants are Ph.D Research Scholars and (27.8%) of their contributions are the Departments in International Business / Corporate Secretary ship.
3. (30.9%) of the Contributions are using Facebook/ WhatsApp along with higher (72.2%) of their respondents used Web Browsers are Google chrome.
4. 47 (48.5%) of respondents' preference of "Very Strongly Agree" Collaborate with Research projects and Teams. It followed by 45 (46.4%) of respondents "Research Collaboration "Strongly Agree" of the respondents respectively.
5. (30.9%) of them respondents purpose of Web 2.0 for Collaborations of Research Communication while (19.6%) of the respondents Web 2.0 Opportunities and Learning for Web 2.0 tools support social interaction in the learning process.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this article, a study of web 2.0 technologies from different perspectives and properties of Web 2.0 and Collaborative Sharing Research Information of Web 2.0 were reviewed. This study also Opportunities and Learning with web 2.0 Networking. The respondents' use of Facebook/ What's App, Twitter/ Instagram, Social bookmark / Tagging, RSS feeds/ Podcasts, Blog/Wiki articles. This discussion should be considered as a researcher observed from the various web 2.0 Research Collaboration analysis and also new areas of emerging technologies. Further research could explore the investigation of Web 2.0 based on technology.

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